

Initial concept for metadata exchange between nfdi.software and other Base4NFDI services

Deliverable D3.2 for nfdi.software NFDI Base project

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Abstract. Here we present our initial concept for metadata exchange with other Base4NFDI service. We first surveyed Base4NFDI projects to find out which Base projects would either consume or produce metadata for research software. Then conducted interviews with consumers and producers to figure out their needs based on common and distinctive metadata elements. Based on surveys and interviews, we present a diagram for a research software metadata exchange across Base4NFDI projects.

Keywords. Research software, metadata, metadata exchange, interoperability

Motivation

Thanks to efforts around Linked Open Data [1] and the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles [2], metadata is nowadays recognized as core to research as it enables exchange between services, institutions, and domains of research. Metadata helps us describe research artifacts (e.g., datasets, software) and connect them to each other. When a semantic approach is used (i.e., following the [Semantic Web](#) and [Resource Data Framework \(RDF\)](#) technologies and recommendations, including, for instance, controlled vocabularies in the

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form of taxonomies, thesauri, ontologies), Knowledge Graphs will emerge naturally from that semantically structured metadata.

Thanks to initiatives around good practices for research software, (e.g., FAIR principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS) [3], software management plans (SMPs) [4–6]), (semantically structured) metadata for research software is becoming more important as it makes it easier to get a quick overview on a software as well as connect it to other research artifacts. Initiatives such as [Codemeta](#) [7] and [Bioschemas](#) [8] (in particular [Bioschemas ComputationalTool](#)), the [Software Ontology](#) [9], the [machine-actionable Software Management Plan](#) (maSMP) metadata schema [10,11], aim to facilitate describing software and its elements to improve, for instance, findability, comparability, and reusability.

Within the scope of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in Germany, there are different initiatives contributing to research software metadata. The Research Software Metadata Working Group [12] has been working on the identification of research software metadata needs in NFDI [13], and, jointly with the NFDI4Base project `nfdi.software`, on an analysis and comparison across different metadata approaches for research software. The NFDI4Base project DMP4NFDI now also includes SMPs together with its corresponding machine-actionable layer in the form of a semantically structured metadata schema [14]. The Mathematical Research Data Initiative (MaRDI) consortium is developing an ontology to represent algorithms [15].

Here we report on the `nfdi.software` concept for a metadata exchange with other NFDI4Base services, corresponding to the deliverable D3.2 of the initialization phase [16].

Approach

We started by emailing a five-question survey, see Box 1, to representative contacts from the other seven NFDI4Base projects at the time: [IAM4NFDI](#) [17,18], [PID4NFDI](#) [19], [TS4NFDI](#) [20,21], [Jupyter4NFDI](#) [22], [DMP4NFDI](#) [14,23], [KGI4NFDI](#) [24], and [RDMTraining4NFDI](#) [25]. Question 4 is a variation of question 2 and was used as a sanity-check on the coherence of answers. Question 3 particularly targeted TS4NFDI, a terminology service that collects and provides information on ontologies and terminologies.

Box 1. Survey sent to other NFDI4Base projects

To find out whether the `nfdi.software` metadata connects anyhow to your own service, I ask you to please answer the following questions:

1. Would it make sense for your service to consume software metadata?
2. Would it make sense for your service to expose software metadata?
3. Would it make sense for your service to expose vocabularies to describe software metadata?
4. Does your service provide (or plan to provide) metadata for software?

5. Does your service provide (or plan to provide) metadata for other research artifacts that could be connected to software metadata?

Based on the results from the survey, we requested a follow-up meeting to those that were either interested in the topic or showed a possible channel for metadata exchange (at least one answer would be “yes” with an explanation aligned to metadata exchange). One of the follow-up meetings, with IAM4NFDI, took place online, while the others happened during an NFDI4Base in-person meeting mid May 2025.

Results

Survey

It took us about one month to collect information from all the NFDI4Base projects. RDMTraining4NFDI answered “no” to all questions, PID4NFDI and IAM4NFDI indicated that the questions did not apply to their service but also expressed interest in knowing more about the metadata exchange plans in nfdi.software. KGI4NFDI answered “maybe” to Question 3, indicating that they would be interested in providing recommendations on metadata schemas commonly used by their users (which was judged as outside the scope of the nfdi.software metadata exchange concept as it was more about listing a metadata schema rather than consuming it or exposing it). TS4NFDI answered “yes” to questions 1, 2, 3, and 4. DMP4NFDI answered “yes” to questions 1, 2, 4, and 5. Jupyter4NFDI answered “yes” to question 1 while “maybe” to questions 2, 4, and 5. All responses showed coherence between questions 2 and 4. Table 1 shows a summary of the answers.

Table 1. Survey responded from Base4NFDI projects

Respondent	Consume metadata	Expose metadata	Expose vocabularies	Provision of metadata for software	Provision of metadata for other research artifacts
KGI4NFDI	No	No	Maybe	No	No
RDMTraining4NFDI	No	No	No	No	No
TS4NFDI	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes, see question 2	Maybe
DMP4NFDI	Yes	Yes	No	Yes, see question 2	Yes
Jupyter4NFDI	Yes	Maybe		See question	Maybe

				2	
PID4NFDI	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
IAM4NFDI	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Based on the results from the survey, we set up a meeting with IAM4NFDI and met with TS4NFDI, DMP4NFDI, Jupyter4NFDI, and PID4NFDI during the Base4NFDI meeting mid May 2025.

Follow-up meetings

Although a metadata schema for nfdi.software has not been yet defined, having one is already recognized as one of the needs for nfdi.software [16,26], also supported by the findings of the Research Software Metadata Working Group [12] and plans on SMPs by the DMP4NFDI Base project [14]. Having a common metadata schema for nfdi.software on the horizon was our basis to discuss with other NFDI4Base projects how a metadata exchange could take place.

Figure 1 depicts a possible research software metadata flow for NFDI4Base projects (in green) based on current status for these projects. Nfdi.software will retrieve metadata from a metadata extractor that will use collections from **TS4NFDI** to enrich metadata with ontological terms tailored to, for instance, NFDI consortia. Collections in TS4NFDI aim at group ontologies based on community needs, making it easier for users to find ontological terms that align to their needs. There is therefore a need for the metadata extractor to support user interaction.

DMP4NFDI and nfdi.software could request enriched metadata from the metadata extractor. DMP4NFDI would do it through its Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) platform and would require metadata compatible with maSMPs. On its side, nfdi.software would also request enriched metadata from the metadata extractor, the exact metadata schema to be defined but most likely compatible with Codemeta (which have been found to be of common use among the researchers [13,26]). Compatibility with Codemeta is ideal as the maSMPs that will be revised and extended by DMP4NFDI are already compatible with it, making the metadata exchange between nfdi.software and DMP4NFDI easier. This also means that the metadata exchange will align to schema.org [27] as Codemeta and maSMP build on top of it.

As **Jupyter4NFDI** offer capabilities to execute software, it makes sense for nfdi.software to offer execution of the software available in the registry in Jupyter4NFDI. As not all software can be executed within the Jupyter Notebooks environment, there is a need for nfdi.software to request an “executability” test from Jupyter4NFDI. To avoid such a test whenever it has been done already, nfdi.software would need to store a flag and timestamp indicating whether or not the software is compatible with Jupyter4NFDI. Whenever a change in the software is registered in nfdi.registry (e.g., a new version), the flag should be reset it as this requires a new “executability” test.

There is also a metadata exchange between DMP4NFDI and IAM4NFDI as RDMO requires user authentication to access the platform. Whenever a user authenticates through IAM4NFDI, the service can provide some metadata about the user. If the user is authenticated through their credentials associated with a university, the metadata will be richer than if, for instance, authenticated via ORCID. Currently, nfdi.software does not require any authentication.

Figure 1. Metadata extraction among Base4NFDI projects based on current setup. Green boxes correspond to Base4NFDI projects while other German-based projects are presented in yellow. Those represented with a continuous line have been already considered for inclusion in nfdi.software during the initialization phase while the other could be considered for the integration phase. Lines start from the resource/agent triggering the action.

In summary, taking into account the current status of the different NFDI4Base services included in Figure 1, there would be a direct metadata exchange between nfdi.software and Jupyter4NFDI (particularly elements related to the “executability” of the software). Nfdi.software and DMP4NFDI, through RDMO, would exchange metadata with a metadata extractor but not directly between the two of them. The metadata extractor would interact with TS4NFDI. RDMO would get some user-related metadata from IAM4NFDI (but not nfdi.software as there is no authentication at the moment).

Further integration

At the moment, nfdi.software and DMP4NFDI are the two consoria that work most closely with research software metadata. However, none of them has planned (yet) for a metadata extractor. A pre-beta version of a metadata extractor for software hosted in GitHub and compatible with Codemeta, Bioschemas ComputationalTool, and maSMP metadata schemas has been recently

released as part of the work done on machine-actionability by NFDI4DataScience consortium [10,11]. The Connected Open-Source Code (ConnOSS) project, a DFG funded project, aims to provide a consistent and comprehensive metadata extraction pipeline, making it easier for registries and aggregators to harvest the metadata [28]. ConnOSS will build on top of the maSMP metadata extractor, making it an ideal option for a metadata extractor serving the needs of Base4NFDI projects. Figure 2 presents a modification introducing ConnOSS as a provider of metadata for research software.

Figure 2. Metadata exchange using ConnOSS as research software metadata provider.

ConnOSS will build on top of the pre-beta release of the maSMP metadata extractor, improving and extending its functionality to extract metadata from GitLab, GitHub, and CodeBerg. It will also get software release metadata from Zenodo. Further metadata enrichment will be done with a Machine Learning model that will also be created as part of ConnOSS.

A further improvement to the Base4NFDI metadata exchange for research software would require a connection between nfdi.software and RDMO. Nfdi.software already considers using a Large Language Model to support a conversational search, which could be extended with Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) with data from RDMO. To this end, nfdi.software would need to provide an (optional) authentication layer, also through IAM4NFDI. In this way,

nfdi.software could require metadata for DMPs and SMPs corresponding to the authenticated user. This metadata would be used as a RAG input, making it possible for nfdi.software to, for instance, provide some software recommendations to the user aligned to its DMP/SMP profile in RDMO. This additional exchange is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Further metadata exchange connecting nfdi.software and DMP4NFDI (through RDMO). Such an exchange would require common IAM4NFDI authentication, depicted in the middle of the figure.

Conclusion

An initial metadata exchange between nfdi.software and other Base4NFDI services is already possible but would require a metadata extractor. To avoid duplication of efforts, ConnOSS would take care of the research software metadata extraction, and corresponding enrichment using data from TS4NFDI. Further exchange between nfdi.software and DMP4NFDI would require authentication through IAM4NFDI.

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